

Assessing Challenges of Birth Registration in Zambia: The Case of Kabwe District

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ABSTRACT: Birth registration is an important aspect when it comes to the protection of children from abuse, promotion of their rights and establishment of their legal identity. However, birth registration in Zambia and Kabwe District had been persistently low, about 16 percent and 10 percent, respectively. Therefore, this research investigated the challenges of birth registration in Kabwe District. The study was descriptive, employing the mixed methods approach and case study design. Both qualitative and quantitative data was collected from primary and secondary sources. The sample included 105 respondents (parents and guardians) and eight (8) service providers. The findings show that the major challenges faced by Government included inadequate enforcement of legal provisions, limited financial resources and lack of mandatory use of birth certificates. The main challenges faced by parents and guardians include; delays in processing birth certificates, lack of information on the importance of birth registration and lack of immediate benefits from birth certificates. Consequently, the Government had put in place fairly effective policy, legal, institutional and technological measures. These measures contributed towards the increase in birth registration coverage in the district from 10 percent in 2017 to 23 percent in 2023. However, the study found that financial and technological measure were inadequate. It recommended provision of adequate financial resources, improved enforcement of the legal and institutional frameworks and to mandate the use of birth certificate for accessing services like school enrolment, social benefits and insurance.

KEYWORDS: Birth Registration, Challenges, Measures, Kabwe District.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this article is to communicate the findings of the research conducted on the challenges of birth registration in Zambia. The topic was, assessing challenges of birth registration in Zambia; the case of Kabwe District. The purpose of the study was to generate relevant information on the challenges of birth registration and make recommendations that may be used by policy makers and actors to improve birth registration in Zambia. The report provides background information, methodology used, findings and recommendations.

Background of the Study Problem

Promotion of the rights and welfare of children has been on top of the global development agendas (UNICEF, 2013:16). This is evidenced by the 1989 United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UN-CRC) which enshrines the rights of children which UN member countries have undertaken to uphold. The UN-CRC recognises birth registration as one important aspect when it comes to the protection of children from abuse, promotion of their rights and establishment of their legal identity. To this effect, Article 7 of the UN-CRC provides that the child shall be registered immediately after birth and shall have the right from birth to a name, the right to acquire a nationality and as far as possible, the right to know and be cared for by his or her parents. The importance of birth registration is further reflected in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially target 16.9 which talks about birth registration as the foundation for legal identity (United Nations, 2018:74). The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of Children (ACRWC), under Article 6.2, equally requires every child to be registered immediately after birth (UNICEF, 2013:7). The proof of age through a birth certificate helps to protect children from abuse, child labour, child trafficking, defilement and child marriage, among others (Pais, 2002:1).

Despite the importance of birth registration, the rate of registration is low to moderate globally. Between 2000 and 2012, the percentage of children under the age of five that were registered at birth only increased from 58 to 65 percent (Deirdre & Hayden, 2018:11). Consequently, almost 230 million children under the age of five are not registered globally. In 2017, 68 percent of countries reported at least 90 percent of births while in Africa, 40 percent of countries have coverage below 50 percent (Yokobori, et al., 2021:1). Sub-Saharan Africa is home to 85 million of children under the age of five who are not registered, while 135 million live in Asia and the Pacific (UNICEF, 2013:15). Within the SADC region, only a few countries like Mauritius (almost 100 percent)

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and South Africa (86 percent) had high birth registration coverage. The rest of the countries, including Zambia, had very low coverage (UNESA, 2010:8).

Birth registration in Zambia started during the colonial era. It was introduced in 1898 through the European, Aliens and Coloured Births and Deaths Registration Act no. 12 of June 1898. However, during this period, the birth registration law left out the indigenous people. It was only in 1973 when the Zambian Government put in place an all-inclusive legal framework that provided for the registration of every birth that occurs within the boundaries of Zambia, regardless of race (Kambole & Silanda, 1994:9).

However, despite these legal and institutional reforms, Zambia had very low birth registration coverage. For instance, the country had a birth registration coverage, for children below the age of five years, of only 10 percent in 2010 before increasing to only 11 percent in 2014 (UNESA, 2010:8; DNRPC & MOH, 2017:1). In 2015, coverage increased to 12 percent before rising to 16 percent in 2016 (DNRPC & MOH, 2017:12), and later, decreasing to 14 percent in 2018 (ZamStats, 2019:15). However, the 2019 Vital Statistics report shows 20 percent as coverage for 2019. Nevertheless, despite these increments, the country had the fourth lowest coverage in the world (UNESA, 2016:13). The main reasons for the low birth registration included lack of knowledge and ignorance among the parents and guardians.

For Kabwe District, in particular, birth registration in 2016 was only 10 percent, below the national average (DNRPC & MOH, 2017:13). This was despite the government establishing the first birth registration centre, outside Lusaka, in Kabwe District in 2015. One major negative effect of this was that Kabwe District lacked accurate vital statistics on births to support evidence-based planning and allocation of resources. In addition, children were put in danger of being shut out of society and denied the right to an official identity and the advantages that came with it (ZamStats, 2019:14).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Birth registration coverage in Zambia is very low, lagging behind most countries in the world. This was despite the country having implemented various measures aimed at improving birth registration coverage (DNRPC & MOH, 2017:). For instance, the 2016 Baseline Survey Report found that only 16 percent of children below five years old were registered, the fourth lowest registration rate in the world (DNRPC & MOH, 2017:12); (UNESA, 2016:32). This implies that over 80 percent of children in Zambia were not registered. In Kabwe District, only 10 percent were registered, leaving 90 percent not registered (DNRPC & MOH, 2017:23). This meant that, Kabwe District, like most districts in the country, lacked accurate vital statistics on births to support evidence-based planning and allocation of resources. Additionally, birth registration is important given the need to protect all children, this is because a child who is not registered is in danger of being shut out of society; denied the right to an official identity, a recognised name, and a nationality (ZamStats, 2019:14). Such children are also at risk to vices such as; child labour and child marriage, they are also in danger of child trafficking or being denied an inheritance (Pais, 2002:5). This creates the need to understand the challenges of birth registration in the country, especially in Kabwe District. Therefore, this study raises the question *“what are the challenges leading to low birth registration in Kabwe District?”*

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study aimed at investigating the challenges of birth registration in Kabwe District. The specific objectives that guided the study were as follows:

- i) To establish the challenges faced by government in providing birth registration services in Kabwe District.
- ii) To identify challenges faced by parents and guardians in accessing birth registration services in Kabwe District.
- iii) To determine the measures put in place by government to improve birth registration in Kabwe District.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RESEARCH

The significance of this research is that it provides detailed information on the challenges of birth registration in Zambia, expected to contribute towards coming up with effective strategies towards improving coverage. This would, in turn, contribute towards the protection of the rights and welfare of children as a birth certificate helps the child to access rights such as; the right to a name, nationality, paternity and inheritance. The government could utilize the findings of this study to improve birth registration, in turn, provide timely vital statistics that contribute to accuracy in planning and implementation of government policies and programmes as well as inclusion of the marginalised in society. The DNRPC and MoH can utilize the data to re-align strategies in order to achieve improved coverage. The findings can also be used by organisations such as UNICEF, World Vision and Plan International in their child protection and welfare promotion activities. Citizens can also be informed on the importance of birth registration. In addition, the international community can use the data from this study to monitor progress towards international targets such as SDGs.

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REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Challenges faced by Governments in Providing Birth Registration Services

Birth registration is done differently in a number of countries and regions, in all cases however, it focuses on meeting the objective of providing legal identity to children and collecting vital statistics relevant for government as it provides social services and implements economic development activities. A review of literature on the challenges of birth registration show a number of challenges faced by the Government of the Republic of Zambia in providing birth registration services. Kambole and Silanda (1994:14) identified bureaucracy, centralised birth registration system, inadequate staffing levels, manual processes and lack of enforcement of birth registration laws as major challenges affecting the provision of birth registration services. Another study by the World Bank Group (2016:12), conducted almost 22 years after Kambole and Silanda's article, identified similar challenges which confirmed that the challenges Zambia was facing had persisted over a number of years, thereby perpetuating low birth registration. The report however, emphasised the failure by government to put in place incentives for birth registration as a major challenge, this is because, as noted by Kambole and Silanda, birth registration had become voluntary as parents and guardians did not have anything forcing them to register their children.

A study by Yokobori et al. (2021:2) also identified a number of challenges faced by the Zambian Government in providing birth registration services such as; inadequate enforcement of laws, lack of effective inter-ministerial cooperation and a confusing division of roles. This was mostly the result of dysfunctional supply side system which resulted in a lack of infrastructure, understaffing and lack of capacity building. Dokovic (2020:7) also identified; lack of online registration, lack of use of mobile technology, lack of unique identifier, lack of digitisation of records and lack of interoperability as some of the areas the country was lagging behind.

Literature from other countries in Africa also identified a number of challenges faced by other governments. The study by Shi, Danquah and Dong (2023:2) identified; lack of capacity to manage existing and emerging technology and interoperability for efficient and effective birth registration, lack of or lagging ICT expertise, and the lack of appropriate infrastructure to permit access and use of modern technology. Ye et al. (2012:2) also identified the lack of political will, instability (war) and the lack of adequate resources as the main factors limiting government efforts in improving civil registration system and birth registration in particular. Globally, the World Bank (2016:3) labelled these challenges as supply-side barriers to birth registration. Like Ye et al. (2012:2), the report also identified poor political commitment, inadequate policies, and a historical lack of investment in civil registration systems. In addition, Pais (2002:12) similarly identified; lack of political will, lack of adequate legislation or its weak enforcement, meagre resources, gender discrimination, geographic barriers, and war or internal conflicts as supply side challenges that impede birth registration. He further argued that, the value of birth registration as a fundamental human right continued to be overlooked, there was continued lack of awareness on the importance of birth registration, as it was not universally perceived as a fundamental right. The end result is a lack of support for birth registration from national and local authorities resulting in low demand from the general public.

Challenges faced by parents and guardians in accessing birth registration services

A review of literature showed that, the challenges faced by government had a spill over effect and translated into most of the challenges faced by parents and guardians in accessing birth registration services. The paper by Kambole and Silanda (1994:14) found that, there was poor enforcement of the law which had resulted in lack of adherence to the legal provisions on birth registration by parents and guardians, as compulsory birth registration had in practice become voluntary. The report further identified the lack of information on the importance of birth registration, delayed processing of birth certificates and lack of compelling factors or incentives. Another report by the CSO and DNRPC (2016:40) identified challenges and measured the proportion of their impact. It found that; ignorance accounted for 82 percent, distance to registration centres accounted for 10 percent and other reasons accounted for only 8 percent. The World Bank Group (2016:9) identified; the lack of incentives and use of alternative documents, low literacy levels, long distances to registration centres for people living in rural areas, protracted process of producing a birth certificate, and the necessity to visit the registration point more than once before a birth certificate can be obtained, among the challenges that affected demand for birth certificates.

Literature from other African countries showed similar challenges, the study by Pelowski et al. (2015:17) noted that, parents and guardians who did not register their children's births had the following characteristics in common: Lived in rural regions, were typically farmers, had no or only primary education, were likely to be older, to have given birth at home, and to have had more children. Like the World Bank (2016:5), Pelowski et al. argued that, the highlighted barriers such as, the issues of cost, lack of knowledge or access were not the major challenges, the report identified the lack of immediate incentives as a major challenge. According to Pelowski et al. (2015:18), parents and guardians made a partially deliberate and conscious decision not to pursue registration because of insufficient immediate benefits. Further review also showed that parents who registered their children were motivated because it was mandatory or highly encouraged by hospital staff, and not necessarily because of immediate benefits. Similarly, Ehab (2015:71) also noted poor access to birth registration services for people who live in rural areas who are impeded by factors such as, long distance, rural poverty, and limited mother's knowledge on birth registration.

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Outside Africa, Kusumaningrum et al. (2016:2) found that the most common barriers faced by parents when attempting to register their children's births included: (1) The formal and informal associated financial costs, (2) the distances of relevant government offices from their houses, (3) the complexity of application procedures, and (4) the general lack of knowledge on how to apply for documents. Another study by Brito et al. (2013:ix) conducted in Bolivia, the Dominican Republic, Guatemala, Nicaragua, and Peru had similar findings to Pelowski et al. (2015:17) and Ehab (2015:71). It found that children from very poor or rural households, with mothers whose own level of education is low, were more likely to lack a birth certificate. It further cited certain unique challenges like in the Dominican Republic where children of foreign and/or undocumented parents faced lower chances of being registered, suggesting an inter-generational transmission of the lack of a legal identity. These findings were further supported by another report by UNICEF (2013:37) which also found that, most unregistered children came from the poorest households, lived in rural areas and had mothers with no or little formal education. It added that, religion and ethnicity equally played a role because in some countries, certain ethnic or religious groups had lower birth registration rates than the national average.

In addition, the World Bank (2016:5) identified similar challenges faced by parents and guardians and labelled them as demand factors that prevent parents and guardians from accessing birth registration services. It validated the earlier claim that, the supply side factors affect the demand for birth registration in a number of ways. For instance, when the supply side barriers make the cost of birth registration high, parents tend to make cost-benefit analysis, and many parents may decide against registration because of the lack of immediate benefits”.

Measures put in place to improve birth registration

The previous two sub-sections presented findings on the challenges that impede birth registration as shown in literature. This subsection present measures put in place to provide birth registration services by looking at birth registration coverage first and then measures. Zamstats (2019:15) indicated that birth registration coverage was 14 percent for the age group 0-5 years. The report further showed that birth registration is much higher in urban (25 percent) than in rural (8 percent) areas. In terms of trends, the percentage of children under the age of 5 years old whose births were registered with the civil authorities increased from 11 percent in 2013-14 to 14 percent in 2018. Globally, birth registration coverage in the Central and Eastern Europe and the Commonwealth of Independent States CEE/CIS was above 98 percent, Latin America and the Caribbean was above 90 percent, and the Middle East and North Africa had above 80 percent. While South, East and West Central Asia as well as Sub Saharan Africa, birth registration coverage was below 50 percent.

The Central Statistical Office (2019:3) identified some of the efforts that were contributing to the slight increase in birth registration coverage, it noted the amendment to the Birth and Death Registration Act (CAP 51) of 1973 with Statutory Instrument (SI) no. 44 of 2016 which provided for decentralised birth certification to lower levels, and the CRVS National Strategic Action Plan to reform and improve civil registration. Similarly, the World Bank Group (2016:4,5) noted the various measures the Zambian Government had put in place, they included: (1) SI 44 of 2016; (2) development of the CRVS National Strategic Action Plan 2015-2019; (3) Memorandum of Understanding on Health Facility Birth Registration desks and (4) Conducting mobile registration exercises to capture rural communities. Yokobori et al. (2021:2) also identified the cooperation between the health sector and civil registration offices in conducting birth registration services as a key measure with potential to contribute towards improving birth registration. Dokovic (2020:4) also identified collaboration between the DNRPC and the MoH which resulted in the establishment of birth registration desks in 615 health facilities as a good measure to cater for the rural population and capturing births at the point of occurrence; and the implementation of the Integrated National Registration Information System, intended to digitilise birth registration.

Interestingly, similar trends were noted in other African countries, UNESA (2010:5,16) found that the main measures put in place to improve birth registration coverage included: (a) legal framework for birth registration, (b) public awareness on the importance of civil registration; (c) providing easy access to birth registration services; and (d) computerizing the civil registration system. Another report by UNESA (2016:43) found that there had been significant increase in birth registration between 2005 and 2015 in most countries in Africa. This was the result of countries implementing measures such as having a country owned civil registration improvement plans and establishing strong links with the health sector as key measures to improving birth registration coverage. Like UNESA (2010:16), Msiska (2019:1282) found that, Malawi had put in place legal and institutional frameworks and commenced the process of conducting mass enrolments to cater for community births and the backlog of unregistered children born before universal and compulsory birth registration was operationalised in 2015. By 2018, however, official statistics showed that only 33 percent of under-five children were registered.

Outside Africa, Sharma et al. (2023:3) in Nepal, identified measures that contributed to increasing birth registration from 35 percent in 2006 to 77 percent in 2019. They included; setting up structural and organisational arrangement to implement targeted policy and programme interventions, introduction of the cash transfer incentive programme to parents for registering their children, decentralised birth registration and issuance of the birth certificates at ward level, raising community awareness regarding the importance of birth registration, building capacity of Local Government bodies to handle birth registration and making birth registration mandatory for school enrolment. Another study by UNICEF (2013:31,32) identified similar measures implemented in

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different countries across the globe. These included legal reforms, awareness-raising, capacity-building, strengthening of birth registration mechanisms and making birth registration free. Others were making a birth certificate as the first step towards citizenship and a pre-requisite to obtaining other important papers. This was supplemented by creating birth registration points in health facilities.

To augment this claim, Pais (2002:5) noted that in Algeria, birth certificates were required for school enrolment. In Malaysia, local police officers, village headmen and midwives were all legally required to notify the District Registrar of any births occurring in their respective areas. In Mauritius, birth registration was a simple and user-friendly procedure and the first copy of the birth certificate was free. In Uzbekistan, the state paid the mother a bonus when she registered her child and birth certificates were needed for immunization, health care and school enrolment. Therefore, the study noted from literature that incentives for birth registration played a key role in improving demand for birth registration. The research noted that, even though similar measures were employed in different jurisdictions, they had varying results depending on the commitment by government towards their adequate implementation, availability of resources and political/social stability of a given country.

Information gaps identified

Literature reviewed provided valuable and important lessons on challenges faced by governments in providing birth registration services, challenges faced by parents and guardians in accessing birth registration services and measures put in place by government to improve birth registration. This research identified a number of gaps in the reviewed literature, especially those on Zambia. The available literature did not provide clear information on what the challenges affecting birth registration really are. This is because, the identified challenges have been similar for close to four decades. This leaves a question of whether the challenges responsible for low birth registration have been correctly identified and addressed. Further, literature did not provide detailed explanation on the adequacy of the policy, legal, institutional, social and technological measures and the reasons why birth registration coverage had remained low, below 20 percent. In addition, it is not clear why government had failed to address the challenges that have existed for almost four decades. Therefore, this research intended to fill these gaps by establishing the real challenges of birth registration in Zambia in general and Kabwe District in particular and to provide explanations on the reasons why there is lack of adherence to legal provisions on the mandatory registration of births. The study further aimed at providing the current levels of birth registration in Kabwe District.

METHODOLOGY

The research was a descriptive study which involved identification of attributes of birth registration challenges with a goal of describing their characteristics. It adopted a mixed methods approach and a non-experimental design which did not require manipulation of variables but making observation on the challenges of birth registration and measures put in place to provide birth registration in Kabwe District as a case study. Kabwe District had a total population of 299,206 people in 2022, comprising 143,892 males and 155,314 females respectively. The district's population of children under the age of five was 33,662, consisting of 16,723 males and 16,940 females (Zamstats, 2022:22). The district also had an estimated 45,675 households (CSO, 2013:65). The total sample size for this research was 113, of which 105 were respondents comprising of parents and guardians in Kabwe District and eight (8) officials from DNRPC and MOH. Quantitative primary data collected from respondents was analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and qualitative primary data collected from key informants was analysed using Thematic Analysis and Narrative Analysis. In addition, secondary data was analysed using Document Analysis.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents research findings on the challenges faced by government in providing birth registration services in Kabwe District, challenges faced by parents and guardians in accessing birth registration services and measures put in place to improve birth registration services.

Levels of Birth Registration

Literature reviewed in Chapter two shows the measures put in place to improve birth registration services, it however, did not show the latest statistics on birth registration services to show whether there had been an improvement in the recent past. However, the study found that birth registration coverage in Kabwe District had improved (more than double) from the 10 percent recorded in 2017 to 23 percent in 2023. This was also higher than the national average of 20 percent for 2019 recorded in the Vital Statistics report of 2020. Out of the registered children, 54 percent were male while 46 percent were female, implying a slightly higher likelihood of a male child being registered than a female child. In addition, the study found that birth registration by place of residences at; 37 percent in urban areas, 31 percent in peri-urban areas and none for children in rural (remote) areas. This implied that there was a significant higher likelihood of an urban or peri-urban birth being registered compared to a rural birth.

Furthermore, the study wanted to understand what motivated the parents and guardians who had their children registered. It found that, 42 percent were encouraged by either their family or friends, 25 percent believed a birth certificate was important for travelling abroad, 25 percent believed that the birth certificate was important for proper identification, while 8 percent believed that the birth

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certificate was needed for school enrolment. However, key informants reiterated that birth certificates were not needed to enrol children in school or obtaining identity documents. This implies that most parents and guardians registered their children for invalid reasons, as the birth certificate was not mandatory for school enrolment or insurance claim.

Challenges faced by government in providing birth registration services

Among other aims, the focus of the study was to understand the challenges of birth registration in Zambia and Kabwe District in particular. This section focuses on discussing the findings on the challenges faced by government in the provision of birth registration services. With regards to institutional challenges, the study found the following;

- Poor collaboration between the MoHAIS and MoH (2018:3). In practice, there were no mechanisms put in place to ensure implementation of the obligations contained in the MoU on health facility birth registration. These obligations were not legally binding on the parties, thus failing to yield the desired results. For example, when the health facility birth registration was introduced, there was effective collaboration between the two ministries. However, with the passage of time, collaboration became poor, mainly due to lack of monitoring and high staff turnover. This is different with what is obtaining in countries such as Malaysia where such collaboration was provided for by law and it led to success in birth registration activities (Pais, 2002:9).
- Inadequate organisation structure of the DNRPC. The inadequate organisation structure threatened the implementation of the CRVS Policy, as it resulted in inadequate capacity and low staffing levels.
- Poor staffing levels; the study observed low staffing levels which negatively affected the capacity of the DNRPC to implement planned activities including supporting health facility birth registration. Similar structural challenges were equally discovered by Siame (2020:55) who found that the DNRPC was deprived of qualified professionals because the staff structure had not grown in tandem with the population growth in Zambia and the subsequent increased demand.
- High health facility staff turnover. This challenge led to trained and experienced health officials being replaced with untrained and inexperienced ones, thereby affecting birth registration in such facilities.

Literature shows that the challenges discussed above are not unique to Zambia, the World Bank (2016:3) argued that the lack of adequate structure and low manpower was the result of a historical lack of investment in CRVS systems in most countries. Ehab (2015:64) also found that despite the existence of structures, governments in most developing countries failed to recruit officers to fill the existing vacancies. This inadequate organisation structure and poor staffing was, likely, the result of birth registration not ranking as a priority area for most governments, including Zambia.

The study also uncovered that the legal framework did not provide for mandatory uses of a birth certificate by parents and guardians when accessing various services. This contributed to lack of incentives for registering births in Zambia such that even when the supply side measures were being implemented, there was nothing compelling parents and guardians to register their children in Kabwe District. In addition, the legal framework in Zambia did not provide for registration of Zambian children born abroad and come back without a birth certificate. This created a situation where such children were left out and remained without legal identity. The findings are similar to other studies conducted in Zambia. For instance, the World Bank Group (2016:12) found that Zambia had a low coverage for birth registration because of a perceived lack of value for having them. In addition, Siame (2020:50) also found that birth registration in Zambia was low due to the widespread use of alternative documents like Under Five Clinic Cards which were accepted when enrolling children for school and when accessing other services.

Financially, there was lack of adequate state funding for effective implementation of the planned strategies to improve birth registration. The study found that, only 30 to 40 percent of the required financial resources were received by DNRPC at provincial level and these funds did not trickle down to the district level. In addition, there was no sustained funding from cooperating partners. This affected the capacity for the district to support health facility birth registration effectively. This inadequate funding was concerning given the fact that most studies, like that of Ehab (2015:64), argued that the magnitude of government commitment to fund necessary activities was key to achieving considerable improvements in birth registration.

Technological challenges included intermittent internet services which contributed to delays in processing birth certificates and the timelines for dispatching certificates back to originating health facilities. In addition, the failure to automate the birth notification process resulted in continued use of manual forms to give notification of a birth. This also contributed to delays in processing application forms in addition to increasing the cost of birth registration on the part of both the Government, and parents and guardians. Countries that succeeded in digitizing the birth registration process did so because of reliable internet connectivity. For instance, in Indonesia, the adoption of advanced technologies such as the Population Administration Information System (SIAC) had been central to the improvement of civil registration. However, success had been hampered by the lack of internet connectivity at the district and sub-district levels (Kusumaningrum et al., 2016:XXV).

Challenges Faced by Parents and Guardians in Accessing Birth Registration Services in Kabwe District

The study found that, challenges like 'language barriers when accessing birth registration services' at 21 percent, 'lack of required supporting documents' at 18 percent and 'long birth registration processes' at only 10 percent did not affect a significant proportion

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of parents and guardians. In this regard, the study concluded that, since most (73 percent) of the parents and guardians did take the necessary steps to register their children's births, they may not have realised that these challenges existed. Further, these percentages become significant when applied against the 23 percent who registered their children.

With regards to financial challenges, since birth registration was free, the study found that, the only financial challenge, which only affected 21 percent, was "lack of funds to meet the costs of making follow-up visits to the registration office" mostly affecting peri-urban and rural populations. This was because, while birth registration and distribution of certificates were decentralised to health facilities in Kabwe District, DNRPC office had less capacity to timely process birth certificates and send them back to the originating health facilities. Parents and guardians would sometimes be referred to follow up birth certificates at DNRPC offices which translated into extra cost. Zambia, like other countries is compliant to the requirement to provide birth registration free of charge. For example, in Malawi, birth registration is free if registered within 6 weeks (Msiska, 2020:1282), in Vietnam and Brazil, birth registration is offered free of charge (UNICEF, 2013:31,32).

In terms of technical and logistical challenges faced by parents and guardians, the research also found that "long distance to registration centres", "lack of correct information on birth registration" and "lack of incentives for birth certificates" affected 30 percent, 55 percent and 54 percent, respectively. It was found that, despite the roping in of some health facilities, inadequate decentralisation meant that some individuals, especially those in rural areas, still lived far from registration centres. In addition, the sensitisation measures seemed to have not been effective while parents and guardians did not see any clearly discernible benefits associated with birth certificates, as they were not needed in accessing important services such as, school enrolment, insurance and health services. The study concluded that, this is as a result of the failure by government to put in place supply side measures that addresses these challenges.

Measures put in Place by Government to Improve Birth Registration in Kabwe District

With regards to measures put in place to improve birth registration in Kabwe District, the research started by assessing the institutional measures and found that the DNRPC was the main institution mandated to provide birth registration services in Zambia. It was present in nine out of 11 districts of Central Province, including Kabwe District. In an effort to improve the institutional mechanisms, the DNRPC and the MoH signed an MoU to allow health facility birth registration, thereby creating access to birth registration for rural communities. The study found that 13 Health Facility based birth registration desks were opened and conducted birth registration services in Kabwe District. In addition, the SZI provided internet and technical support to the DNRPC to support birth registration. The collaboration among these institutions leveraged on existing capacities in each institution to supplement the efforts of the mandate holder, the DNRPC.

The findings of the study on the collaboration between the DNRPC and the MoH to register births in health facilities made good reading as it responds to the need to bridge the gap on the high number of unregistered rural births (DNRPC, 2020:6). Since health facilities are spread all over the country, it allowed parents and guardians to easily register the births of their children in health facilities immediately after giving birth rather than having to travel to one DNRPC office in the district (Yokobori, et al., 2021:6). This is also ideal since most births (84 percent) in Zambia occurred in health facilities (ZamStats, 2019:8). These findings are similar to results from a study by Yokobori, et al (2021:2) who found effective cooperation between the health sector and civil registration offices with regards to improving birth registration in Zambia. And thus, recommended opening up more registration points in health facilities. The findings showed that these institutional measures compared well with other countries and had potential to greatly contribute to increasing birth registration in Kabwe District.

The study also found that, the policy and legal framework included the National CRVS Policy which provided high level direction for improving civil registration in Zambia and Kabwe in particular. It also included the Birth and Death Registration Act Cap 51 of the laws of Zambia which provided for mandatory registration of births and deaths occurring within the boundaries of Zambia using decentralised registration and centralised certification. Further, in an effort to strengthen the legal framework, Statutory Instrument No. 44 of 2016 was put in place to address the gaps in the main Act by providing for improved birth notification forms and decentralised birth certification. The introduction of the SI enabled the Country to compare well with other countries where the legal framework provides for decentralised issuance of birth certificates, making them easier to access (PLAN International, 2017:39). In countries like Nepal, laws even provided for decentralised certification at ward level (Sharma et al., 2023:3). The study concluded that the legal framework was generally robust and comprehensive enough to improve birth registration in Kabwe District. However, gaps in the legal framework included; lack of provisions for incentives to register births and failure to cover for the registration of Zambian children born in other jurisdictions but not registered before coming back to Zambia.

The study further found that the only financial measure put in place to improve birth registration in Kabwe District was the allocation made in the national budget. Further probing revealed that this state funding was inadequate to fund birth registration activities as it only covered 30 to 40 percent of the required resources. In terms of technological measures, Kabwe District was found to have implemented the INRIS through which the DNRPC had automated the registration and certification process. This was a major improvement to the effectiveness and efficiency of processing of birth certificates at district level. However, the study found that the INRIS did not include automation of notification. That is, parents and guardians were still required to fill in manual notification

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forms which were later authorised manually and thereafter entered in the system. This had the potential to negatively affect the registration process in terms of time, cost as well as management of the notification forms. Existing literature recognises the importance of utilising digital methods to improve birth registration. Digital platforms provide new channels for service delivery, public engagement, and feedback, and increased efficiency (Shi, Danquah, & Dong, 2022:2,6). Globally, digital technology has been used as an enabler to birth registration as it, not only, enables supply of effective and efficient birth registration services, but also increase the demand for the service itself (PLAN International, 2017:31).

Based on the findings discussed in this section on the measures put in place to improve birth registration in Kabwe District, the study concluded that the institutional, policy and legal measures had the ability to help improve birth registration in Kabwe District. However, the financial and technological measures needed major improving while the legal framework needed minor amendments.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i) Provide for legally binding mandatory uses of birth certificates when accessing various services. This will introduce clear legal uses of birth certificates.
- ii) Given the positive impact of the health facility-based birth registration, there is need to strengthen the operations of health facility birth registration desks by providing necessary support and to establish additional desks across the country.
- iii) The Government should consider including civil registration (birth registration) as part of the curriculum for primary and secondary education. Such a move will have positive long-term impact for the Zambian people.
- iv) There is need to amend the law to include provisions for the registration of Zambian children born abroad but return to Zambia without a birth certificate from their country of birth. This will address the present situation where such children are left out.
- v) There is need to automate the birth notification under the INRIS to improve the speed of birth registration and to make it less costly for both Government and parents and guardians.
- vi) Government should fully implement the DNRPC Organisation Structure to improve staffing levels in Districts and to provide adequate office and internet connectivity infrastructure.

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